

STUDIES IN THE NEGATIVELY CHARGED COLLOIDAL SOLUTIONS OF VARIOUS FERRIC SALTS. PART VI. NEGATIVELY CHARGED FERRIC PHOSPHATE SOL

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Negatively charged ferric phosphate sols have been prepared and studied. The sols were prepared by adding potassium dihydrogen phosphate solution to ferric chloride solution and dispersing the precipitate of ferric phosphate by caustic soda in presence of glucose or glycerine. The glucose-peptised sol has the composition $8\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and the glycerine-peptised sol, $5\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Various other characteristics of the sols have been investigated.

The study of the positively charged sols and gels of ferric phosphate has attracted the attention of numerous workers. Holmes and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 1970; 1918, 40, 1014) have observed that freshly precipitated ferric phosphate can be peptised by methylamine, aqueous ammonia, ferric chloride or sulphate and nitric or hydrochloric acid. Varma and Parkash (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 205, 241) investigated the peptisation of ferric phosphate by ferric chloride in presence of various peptising agents such as glucose, glycerine and urea; Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 391; 1930, 7, 417) studied changes in the viscosity of the sol during setting to a jelly. The rhythmic precipitation of the hydrogel was investigated by Chatterji and Dhar (*Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 40, 98) and Banerji and Ghosh (*ibid.*, 1933, 65, 37) determined the viscosities of the sol at various pressures. The kinetics of sol-gel transformation of ferric phosphate was investigated by Dube and Prakash (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, 217, 284). Prakash (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1933, 8, 243) found no marked change in the magnetic susceptibility of ferric phosphate sol when it was converted into a gel. The sols and gels of ferric phosphate, studied so far, are positively charged and no attempt seems to have been made to prepare and investigate the negatively charged sols of ferric phosphate. Sell (*Proc. Camb. Phil. Soc.*, 1904, 12, 388) mentions the formation of a negatively charged brownish red sol, obtained by dissolving ferric phosphate in diammonium hydrogen phosphate in presence of ammonia.

In a recent publication, Mushran (*Curr. Sci.*, 1946, 15, 224) has observed that if an excess of potassium dihydrogen phosphate solution is added to a ferric chloride solution, a permanent precipitate of ferric phosphate is obtained, which can be easily dispersed by caustic soda to give a bright red sol of ferric phosphate which bears a negative charge, as shown by the cataphoretic method. The peptisation is greatly facilitated by the addition of glucose or glycerine. In previous communications of this series, Mushran and Prakash (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 111, 391, 413, 445) have described the negatively charged colloidal solutions of various ferric

salts. In this paper observations have been made regarding the compositions and properties of the negatively charged ferric phosphate sols. An idea of the peptisation of ferric phosphate by caustic soda in presence of glycerine or glucose can be had from the following figures :

1.0-2.0 C.c. of a ferric chloride solution (30.36 of Fe_2O_3 per litre) when mixed with 1.0 to 3.0 c.c. of a 10% potassium dihydrogen phosphate solution in presence of 1.0 to 3.0 c.c. of 20% glucose solution, requires 3.8 to 4.2 c.c. of $N\text{-NaOH}$ solution (total volume 10 c.c.) to bring about complete peptisation in half an hour.

1.0-2.0 C.c. of the same ferric chloride solution, when mixed with 1.0 to 3.0 c.c. of the potassium dihydrogen phosphate solution in presence of 1.0 to 3.0 c.c. of glycerine, requires 2.0 to 4 c.c. of $N\text{-NaOH}$ solution (total volume 10 c.c.) to bring about complete peptisation in half an hour.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sol A was prepared by mixing 40 c.c. of a ferric chloride solution (30.36 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre), 40. c.c. of a 10% potassium dihydrogen phosphate solution and 20 c.c. of a 20% glucose solution and 84 c.c. of $N\text{-NaOH}$ solution. The total volume was raised to 200 c.c. The sol was dialysed for 15 days.

Sol B was prepared by mixing 40 c.c. of the same ferric chloride solution, 40 c.c. of 10% potassium dihydrogen phosphate solution, 20 c.c. of glycerine and 80 c.c. of $N\text{-NaOH}$ solution. The total volume was raised to 200 c.c. The sol was dialysed for 15 days.

Composition of the Sols

The amounts of iron in a known volume of the sol was estimated by dissolving the sol in hydrochloric acid and reducing with stannous chloride, and the ferrous iron was titrated against potassium dichromate (vide Part I of this series, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 111).

The total phosphate in a known volume of the sol was estimated gravimetrically as ammonium phosphomolybdate.

To determine the amount of the phosphate in the combined state with iron, a known volume of the sol was cataphoretically coagulated, by taking the sol in a U-tube with platinum electrodes and passing a current when the sol was coagulated at the anode. The total coagulum was collected, washed and estimated for phosphate. The coagula were also obtained by the use of potassium chloride and the concordance of the results showed that the equilibrium between the free and the combined phosphate was not appreciably altered. The combined iron corresponding to this

amount of phosphate was calculated on the assumption that the ferric phosphate was FePO_4 . The rest of the iron was present as hydrated ferric oxide. From the ratio of the free to the combined iron, the empirical formula of the sol was calculated. The viscosity of the sol was measured by the Ostwald's method at 30° , and the amount of bound water was calculated from the Hatschek's equation (vide Part I of this series, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

Per litre.	Sol A Glucose sol.	Sol B Glycerine sol.
Total iron	1.1636g.	1.1724g.
Total phosphate (PO_4)	0.5430	0.5772
Combined phosphate (PO_4)	0.2260	0.2200
Free phosphate (PO_4)	0.3150	0.2572
Combined iron	0.1340	0.1660
Free iron	1.0296	0.9864
Viscosity of sol	0.00836	0.00664
Viscosity of water	0.00803	0.00803
Water, bound	0.06151	0.3519
Empirical formula	$8\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$5\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$

The sols were coagulated cataphoretically as well as by 0.1N-potassium chloride, centrifuged and the H^+ -ion concentration of the supernatant aqueous layers was determined by Hildebrand's hydrogen electrode. The following *pH* values were recorded.

Sol A	Sol B
<i>pH</i> 7.03 (coagulated by KCl)	7.04 (coagulated by KCl)
7.20 (cataphoretically coagulated)	7.18 (cataphoretically coagulated)

Conductivities of the Sols

In Table II are recorded the observations on the conductivities of these sols at various dilutions, at various temperatures, and also the values on ageing.

TABLE II A
Conductivity values at dilutions (30°).

Dilutions.	Conductivity of sol A.	Conductivity of sol B.	Dilutions.	Conductivity of sol A.	Conductivity of sol B.
Original sol (X)	3.52×10^{-4} mho	2.00×10^{-4} mho	X/2	1.78×10^{-4} mho	1.40×10^{-4} mho
5X/6	3.01	2.20	X/3	1.26	1.01
2X/3	2.37	1.72	X/6	0.81	0.48

TABLE II B

Conductivity values on ageing. (30°)

Date.	Conductivity of		Date.	Conductivity of	
	sol A.	sol B.		sol A.	sol B.
18.9.45	3.53×10^{-4} mho	2.60×10^{-4} mho	21.12.45	3.75×10^{-4} mho	2.70×10^{-4} mho
20.10.45	3.58	2.62	2.3.46	4.00	2.91
20.11.45	3.65	2.67	4.4.46	4.02	2.85

TABLE II C

Conductivity values at diff. temperatures.

Temp.	Glucose sol (A)		Glycerine sol (B)	
	Conducty.	Diff. per 5°.	Conducty.	Diff. per 5°.
40°	4.17×10^{-4} mho		3.08×10^{-4} mho	
35°	3.64	0.88	2.60	0.38
30°	3.52	0.82	2.60	0.20
25°	3.19	0.88	2.31	0.20
20°	2.86	0.38	2.05	0.25
Temp. of zero conductance (extrapolated)				
		-22.0°		-20.5°
Temp. coeff. per 1°		0.068		0.080

From the above data the sols appear to be pretty stable on dilution, as the conductivities of the sols are very nearly proportional to the dilutions. The conductivities of the sols increase with age. The temperatures of zero conductance range between -22.0° and -20.5°.

Extinction Coefficients of the Sols

Extinction coefficients of the sols were determined by the Nutting spectrophotometer at different dilutions and at different wave-lengths and the results are recorded in Table III (X stands for the original undiluted sol).

TABLE III

Wave-lengths.	Sol A				Sol B			
	X.	X/2.	X/4.	X/8.	X.	X/2.	X/4.	X/8.
5000 μ	3.00	1.60	0.90	0.45	3.00	1.02	0.51	0.26
5200	2.50	1.25	0.66	0.33	1.60	0.82	0.42	0.21
5400	1.80	0.95	0.48	0.24	1.20	0.61	0.30	0.15
5600	1.40	0.72	0.36	0.18	0.85	0.43	0.22	0.11
5800	1.00	0.52	0.27	0.14	0.61	0.31	0.16	0.08
6000	0.72	0.36	0.18	0.10	0.45	0.23	0.12	0.06
6200	0.54	0.27	0.14	0.08	0.34	0.18	0.09	0.05
6400	0.45	0.24	0.12	0.07	0.20	0.15	0.07	0.04

From these data the sols appear to obey Beer's law i.e. the extinction coefficients are almost proportional to the dilutions. This suggests that the sols are quite stable and do not hydrolyse during the process of dilution. The results on the conductivities of the sols at different dilutions (Table II A) also show the similar behaviour.

Coagulation of the Sols

In Table IV are recorded the minimum amounts of electrolytes necessary to coagulate 1c.c. of the sols in a total volume of 10 c.c., the time allowed in each case being 30 minutes.

TABLE IV

Electrolytes.	Amount necessary to coagulate		Electrolytes.	Amount necessary to coagulate	
	sol A.	sol B.		sol A.	sol B.
0.1N-NaCl	1.40 c.c.	1.20 c.c.	0.005N-BaCl ₂	0.70 c.c.	0.60 c.c.
0.1N-KCl	1.20	1.00	0.005N-Sr(NO ₃) ₂	0.80	0.80
0.1N-KNO ₃	1.20	1.00	0.004N-AlCl ₃	0.60	0.50
0.1N-KI	1.20	1.00			

The coagulating powers of the ions thus fall in the following series :
 NaCl < KCl, KI, KNO₃ < Sr(NO₃)₂ < BaCl₂ < AlCl₃.

The effect of dilution on the coagulation values has also been investigated and the results are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Electrolytes.	Amount necessary to coagulate (c.c.)					
	Sol A.			Sol B.		
	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.
0.1N-NaCl	1.40	1.60	1.80	1.20	1.40	1.60
0.1N-KCl	1.20	1.30	1.40	1.00	1.10	1.20
0.1N-KNO ₃	1.20	1.30	1.40	1.00	1.10	1.20

From the above table it is evident that the sols obey the Schulze-Hardy rule for the coagulation with electrolytes. They show the normal behaviour with dilution.

Positively Charged Ferric Phosphate Sols

The sols were prepared by peptising freshly precipitated ferric phosphate in excess of ferric chloride. In Table VI are recorded the compositions of some

positively charged sols of ferric phosphate. Sol A was prepared by mixing 40 c.c. of a ferric chloride solution (69.84 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre) and 40 c.c. of 10% KH_2PO_4 solution. The total volume was kept at 90 c.c. The sol was dialysed for 3 days. Sol B was prepared by mixing 40 c.c. of ferric chloride solution (of the same strength) and 30 c.c. of 10% KH_2PO_4 solution. The total volume was kept at 90 c.c. The sol was dialysed for 3 days.

TABLE VI

Per litre.	Sol A.	Sol B.
Total iron	15.0768 g.	12.7368 g.
Combined phosphate (PO_4)	19.4000	17.2500
Combined iron	11.4000	8.9000
Free iron	3.6768	4.7768
Viscosity of sol (30°)	0.00872	0.00882
Bound water	0.4953	0.3207
Empirical formula	$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$5\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 19\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Cl ⁻ ions per litre	1.8900 g.	3.9000 g.

DISCUSSION

Usually when a dipotassium phosphate solution is added to an excess of ferric chloride, the substance precipitated is monohydrogen phosphate according to the following equation :

When the precipitation is carried out with potassium dihydrogen phosphate, the precipitate obtained is very likely ferric dihydrogen phosphate :

This is the expected composition of the positively charged ferric phosphate sol, obtained by peptising the ferric hydrogen phosphate with ferric chloride. But in the case of the negatively charged sols, which are prepared in presence of excess of alkali, the constitution probably corresponds to ferric *orthophosphate*, FePO_4^- :

In the course of dialysis most of the sodium phosphate, thus formed, is eliminated but the sol still contains a considerable amount of ferric phosphate. A portion of ferric phosphate is also hydrolysed during the course of peptisation or dialysis and the following equilibria are ultimately maintained :

The compositions of the negatively and the positively charged sols are given below. For comparison, positively charged sols have also been expressed in terms of FePO_4 .

Negatively charged.

Positively charged.

From these compositions it is clear that the positively charged ferric phosphate sols contain a larger content of phosphate combined with iron than the negatively charged sols.

The temperature coefficients of the negatively charged ferric phosphate sols are of interest. The temperature coefficients are given below along with the conductivities at 35° .

	Conductivity at 35° .	Tem. coeff. per 1° .
(Glucose sol (A))	3.84×10^{-4} mhrs	0.088
Glycerine sol (B)	2.80	0.050

The temperature coefficient of sol A is thus 1.72% of the conductance at 35° , and that of sol B is 1.78% of the conductance at 35° i.e., the temperature coefficients per 1° of the sols are always less than 2% of the conductances at 35° .

In this paper the various characteristics of the negatively charged ferric phosphate sols have been reported. From the results recorded in the foregoing tables, the following observations may be summarised :

1. The electrical conductivities of the sols are proportional to the dilutions.
2. The electrical conductivities of the sols are linear functions of temperatures. The temperatures of zero conductance range between -22.0° and -20.5° .
3. The temperature coefficients of conductivity per 1° of the sols are always less than 2% of the conductances at 35° .
4. The ageing effect, as studied by the conductivity values, is equally prominent in both the sols. The conductivities increase when the sols age.
5. The extinction coefficients are proportional to the dilutions. The sols obey Beer's law.
6. The pH values of the dispersion medium lie between 7.03 and 7.20 showing that the sols are slightly basic to the stabilising hydroxide ions.
7. The sols obey the Schulze-Hardy rule for the coagulation with electrolytes. They show the normal behaviour with dilution.

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